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DYNAMICAL SMOOTHING:

Task description for a study of alternative approaches

L Lindegren

SUMMARY

Dynamical smoothing means that a smooth function, such as a polynomial, is used to represent the attitude motion of HIPPARCOS over periods up to several minutes, rather than a discrete, frame-by-frame model, as in the baseline solution. The expected accuracy gain is substantial, especially for the brighter stars, but the computations are also more complex and time consuming. At present, programs for the so-called set solutions are developed for the discrete model only, but it may be possible to generalize them at a later stage to include the possibility of dynamical smoothing. It is not obvious, however, that this is the most efficient approach. At least two alternatives should be considered: (i) to reverse the present method, that is to eliminate the star positions rather than the attitude, and (ii) to use the discrete solution as input for an iterative (approximate) improvement by posterior smoothing of the attitude. Especially the second approach might be extremely attractive if it can be shown to give a reasonable approximation to the strict solution. This question is best studied by numerical simulations, which must not necessarily be of full scale. However, the strict solution must also be implemented for comparison. The task is then (a) to write experimental programs for the three kinds of solution (discrete, with posterior smoothing, and a strict smoothing) and (b) to compare the performances in terms of accuracy and computational efficiency. The results of this study would be the basis for a decision on the eventual method to be used by NDAC. Simulated input data and basic routines for calculating residuals and partial derivatives will be available. FORTRAN 77 should be used throughout.

This paper concentrates on a fairly detailed specification of the mathematical/numerical problem without requiring very much prior knowledge of the HIPPARCOS mission as a whole.

1. THE SET SOLUTION

A central part of the HIPPARCOS data reductions is the *set solution*, *great-circle reduction*, or *Step 1*. These are the names variously used for essentially the same process. Mathematically, it is a simple least-squares estimation of certain parameters describing the stellar positions, rotational motion (attitude) of the satellite, and optical-geometrical properties of the telescope. The process uses as input data collected in a distinct time interval, called a *set*, of about 6 to 12 hours.

Observations

The main input for the set solution, or the 'observations', consist of instantaneous, one-dimensional locations of stellar images on the primary grid. The grid consists of 2688 parallel and equidistant slits in a square field of view of $0.9^\circ \times 0.9^\circ$. The star images move across the field in about 20 s, normal to the slits, due to the slow spin of the satellite. One of the slits near the field centre is arbitrarily chosen as origin for the locations. These are expressed as a continuous *grid coordinate*, e.g. $G = -847.1816$ means that the image is between the 848th and 847th slit previous to the origin slit.

There are typically 3 to 5 programme stars on the primary grid at any time. Due to the optical beam combiner in front of the telescope, some of these may belong to the preceding field ($f = +1$), the others then to the following field ($f = -1$). Stars observed together can thus in reality be widely separated on the sky.

The determination of grid coordinates is not part of the set solution. We can think of it as a Fourier analysis of the modulated light recorded behind the grid, where the phase estimate is obtained independently for (usually) all the programme stars on the grid. This analysis is made independently for short stretches of data, called *frames*, and having a duration of $32/15 = 2.1333..$ s. The different programme stars are interlaced in a frame, so that it is possible to refer their phases (and grid coordinates) to a common instant in the frame, namely the *frame mid-time*.

There is a useful convention within NDAC, according to which stars, sets, and frames are uniquely defined by identification numbers symbolized by i , j , and k , respectively. Thus G_{ik} means the grid coordinate measured for star i in frame k ; this measurement refers to the frame mid-time T_k . With some slight abuse of common mathematical symbols, we may take $i \in j$ to mean that the star i was observed in set j ;

$i \in k$ that the star was observed in frame k , and $k \in j$ that frame k belongs to set j . The observational input for set j can now be written compactly as follows:

$$\left\{ k, T_k, \{i, f_{ik}, G_{ik}, \sigma_{G_{ik}} \mid i \in k\} \mid k \in j \right\} \quad (1)$$

Here f_{ik} is the field index (± 1 for preceding/following field) of the observation and $\sigma_{G_{ik}}$ its estimated standard deviation.

Observation model

The observation model is a set of rules for calculating the observed quantity (in this case, G_{ik}) as function of time and the state variables (parameters) describing the object and instrument and their motions.

The relevant parameters are:

- (i) the astrometric parameters for the object (position, proper motion, and parallax); here represented by the vector $\mathbf{a}_i$;
- (ii) the attitude motion of the satellite, represented by three Euler angles being continuous functions of time: $\nu(T)$, $\xi(T)$, $\Omega(T)$;
- (iii) the optical-geometrical properties of the telescope, here represented by (constant) vector of transformation coefficients $\mathbf{d}_j$ for mapping the primary grid in terms of direction cosines in the telescope system. The vector is indexed by the set number because we generally assume that the transformation may be different for each set (but still constant within the set).

The observation model is thus the function

$$G_{ik} \doteq G[T_k; \mathbf{a}_i, \nu(T_k), \xi(T_k), \Omega(T_k), \mathbf{d}_{j(k)}] \quad (2)$$

approximating the measured grid coordinate, provided that the model is adequate and the parameter values correct.

There is no need to go into the explicit formulae involved in (2); they can be found e.g. in Ref. 1-3. If we regard specifically the data collected in a limited time interval such as a set, and consider that the measurements are essentially one-dimensional (along the scanning great circle), it is obvious that only certain combinations of

parameters have a 'strong' influence on the grid coordinate, while other combinations may have a much weaker effect. For the astrometric parameters, the relevant combination is the *abscissa* (a_{ij}), or the instantaneous component of the geocentric position along the mean scanning direction of the set. For the attitude, it happens to be just the third Euler angle (Ω), which measures the rotation of the satellite around its axis. Thus a simplified version of the observation model is

$$G_{ik} \doteq G[T_k; a_{ij}, \delta\Omega(T_k), \mathbf{d}_{j(k)} \mid \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_i, \tilde{v}(T_k), \tilde{\xi}(T_k), \tilde{\Omega}(T_k)] \quad (3)$$

in which only the strong components a_{ij} , $\delta\Omega$ (a correction to $\tilde{\Omega}$), and $\mathbf{d}_j$ are retained among the principal arguments. The ancillary arguments to the right of the vertical bar are still needed to compute the grid coordinate, but to much less accuracy; therefore, approximate (a priori) values can be used, as indicated by the tilde $\sim$.

Observation equation

The set solution is a least-squares estimation of the following unknowns:

- (a) star abscissae a_{ij} , $i \in j$
- (b) corrections to the third attitude angle $\delta\Omega(T_k)$, $k \in j$
- (c) transformation coefficients $\mathbf{d}_j$.

By linearization, the observation equation is

$$\frac{\partial G_{ik}^c}{\partial a_{ij}} \Delta a_{ij} + \frac{\partial G_{ik}^c}{\partial \delta\Omega_k} \Delta \delta\Omega(T_k) + \frac{\partial G_{ik}^c}{\partial \mathbf{d}_j} \Delta \mathbf{d}_j + v_{ik} = G_{ik} - G_{ik}^c \quad (4)$$

with G_{ik}^c denoting the calculated grid coordinate [using (3)]. v_{ik} is white observation noise with expectation $E(v_{ik}) = 0$ and variance $E(v_{ik}^2) = \sigma_{G_{ik}}^2$.

Thus far we have not specified the analytical form for the function $\delta\Omega(T)$. The value of the function is only needed at frame mid-times, $T = T_k$. The simplest (and most conservative) model is then to regard each $\delta\Omega_k \equiv \delta\Omega(T_k)$ as an independent unknown in the least-squares solution. This is the discrete model or *geometrical set solution*. From a theoretical standpoint, the 'best' choice would be a dynamical model,

incorporating the equations of motion and a realistic model of perturbing torques. This is dynamical smoothing in the purest sense. Practically, however, this approach may have important drawbacks: it is complicated, it may not be flexible enough to accommodate unmodelled or unexpected perturbations, and it could easily give rise to numerical problems e.g. if some parameter combinations are inestimable. Moreover, computer simulations of the attitude motion show that $\Omega(T)$ can be represented just as well with simple and well-behaved functions (trigonometric series, polynomials, or splines) and using only moderately more free parameters per unit time.

Consequently, as an alternative to the discrete model we may use a simple analytical representation of $\Omega(T)$ in finite intervals. This could perhaps be termed *numerical smoothing* in contrast to the truly dynamical approach, but for historic reasons we still call it dynamical smoothing. A possible model is the following. Define *superframe* κ to be an uninterrupted sequence of frames, $\kappa = \{k, k+1, \dots, k+m_\kappa-1\}$, where $m_\kappa \geq 1$. Then assume a polynomial of degree n_κ ,

$$\delta\Omega(T_k) = \sum_{l=0}^{n_\kappa} (T_k - T_\kappa)^l \delta\Omega_{\kappa l}, \quad k \in \kappa \quad (5)$$

where $\delta\Omega_{\kappa l}$, $l = 0, \dots, n_\kappa$ are independent unknowns in the set solution. T_κ is the superframe mid-time. Note that for $\kappa = k$, $m_\kappa = 1$, $n_\kappa = 0$ we obtain the discrete model again.

The division of a set into superframes is a somewhat arbitrary procedure. It could be governed by a few simple parameters and rules, e.g.: maximum length ($\max m_\kappa$); maximum degree ($\max n_\kappa$); no superframe of length $m_\kappa > 1$ may contain a jet thrust; $n_\kappa \leq (m_\kappa - 1)/2$.

Given the superframe structure, the set solution (set j) can now be defined as the minimization of

$$SSR = \sum_{k \in j} \sum_{i \in k} (v_{ik}/\sigma_{Gik})^2 \quad (6)$$

by independent adjustment of the unknowns in (3), namely

$$\{ a_{ij} \mid i \in j \}, \{ \delta\Omega_{\kappa 0}, \dots, \delta\Omega_{\kappa n_\kappa} \mid \kappa \in j \}, \mathbf{d}_j \quad (7)$$

2. SOLUTION METHODS

Only solution methods based on normal equations are taken up here, since other direct methods (using orthogonal transformations, for instance) seem to be computationally less efficient. Iterative methods are probably also unfavourable, or perhaps better suited for a very fast computer with relatively little primary memory.

Strict solution: elimination of attitude

These are obtained if the superframe equations (5) are directly substituted into the observation equations (4). The resulting equations for superframe κ can be written, in matrix notation,

$$\mathbf{B}_\kappa \Delta\Omega_\kappa + \mathbf{C}_\kappa \Delta\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{D}_\kappa \Delta\mathbf{d} + \mathbf{v}_\kappa = \mathbf{e}_\kappa \quad (8)$$

The dimensions of the various matrices are as follows:

$$\begin{array}{lll} \mathbf{B}_\kappa (N_\kappa, n_\kappa+1) & \Delta\Omega_\kappa (n_\kappa+1, 1) & \mathbf{v}_\kappa (N_\kappa, 1) \\ \mathbf{C}_\kappa (N_\kappa, N_\alpha) & \Delta\mathbf{a} (N_\alpha, 1) & \mathbf{e}_\kappa (N_\kappa, 1) \\ \mathbf{D}_\kappa (N_\kappa, N_d) & \Delta\mathbf{d} (N_d, 1) & \end{array}$$

where N_κ is the number of observations in the superframe, N_α the number of abscissae in the set, and N_d the number of transformation coefficients in $\mathbf{d}_j$.

Forming the complete system of normal equations for the $N_\Omega + N_\alpha + N_d$ unknowns [with $N_\Omega = \sum_{\kappa \in j} (n_\kappa+1)$], we get

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B}_1^t \mathbf{B}_1 & & \emptyset & \mathbf{B}_1^t \mathbf{C}_1 & \mathbf{B}_1^t \mathbf{D}_1 \\ & \mathbf{B}_2^t \mathbf{B}_2 & & \mathbf{B}_2^t \mathbf{C}_2 & \mathbf{B}_2^t \mathbf{D}_2 \\ & & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \emptyset & & & \mathbf{B}_K^t \mathbf{B}_K & \mathbf{B}_K^t \mathbf{C}_K & \mathbf{B}_K^t \mathbf{D}_K \\ \mathbf{C}_1^t \mathbf{B}_1 & \mathbf{C}_2^t \mathbf{B}_2 & \dots & \mathbf{C}_K^t \mathbf{B}_K & \sum_{\kappa} \mathbf{C}_\kappa^t \mathbf{C}_\kappa & \sum_{\kappa} \mathbf{C}_\kappa^t \mathbf{D}_\kappa \\ \mathbf{D}_1^t \mathbf{B}_1 & \mathbf{D}_2^t \mathbf{B}_2 & \dots & \mathbf{D}_K^t \mathbf{B}_K & \sum_{\kappa} \mathbf{D}_\kappa^t \mathbf{C}_\kappa & \sum_{\kappa} \mathbf{D}_\kappa^t \mathbf{D}_\kappa \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta\Omega_1 \\ \Delta\Omega_2 \\ \vdots \\ \Delta\Omega_K \\ \Delta\mathbf{a} \\ \Delta\mathbf{d} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B}_1^t \mathbf{e}_1 \\ \mathbf{B}_2^t \mathbf{e}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{B}_K^t \mathbf{e}_K \\ \sum_{\kappa} \mathbf{C}_\kappa^t \mathbf{e}_\kappa \\ \sum_{\kappa} \mathbf{D}_\kappa^t \mathbf{e}_\kappa \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

For simplicity we may assume that the superframes in the set are numbered $\kappa = 1, 2, \dots, K$.

The upper-left $N_{\Omega} \times N_{\Omega}$ part of the normal equations matrix is block diagonal, i.e. zero except in the small squares [of size $(n_{\kappa}+1) \times (n_{\kappa}+1)$] along the diagonal. Assuming that all the $B'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa}$ are positive definite (which they normally are), we can eliminate all the attitude unknowns from the system. The resulting (contracted) system of order $(N_{\alpha} + N_d)^2$ is

$$\sum_{\kappa} \begin{bmatrix} C'_{\kappa\kappa}C_{\kappa\kappa} - C'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa}(B'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa})^{-1}B'_{\kappa\kappa}C_{\kappa\kappa} & C'_{\kappa\kappa}D_{\kappa\kappa} - C'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa}(B'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa})^{-1}B'_{\kappa\kappa}D_{\kappa\kappa} \\ D'_{\kappa\kappa}C_{\kappa\kappa} - D'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa}(B'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa})^{-1}B'_{\kappa\kappa}C_{\kappa\kappa} & D'_{\kappa\kappa}D_{\kappa\kappa} - D'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa}(B'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa})^{-1}B'_{\kappa\kappa}D_{\kappa\kappa} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta a \\ \Delta d \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{\kappa} \begin{bmatrix} C'_{\kappa\kappa}e_{\kappa\kappa} - C'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa}(B'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa})^{-1}B'_{\kappa\kappa}e_{\kappa\kappa} \\ D'_{\kappa\kappa}e_{\kappa\kappa} - D'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa}(B'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa})^{-1}B'_{\kappa\kappa}e_{\kappa\kappa} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

The form of this system, with the summations over κ put outside the brackets, shows that it can be accumulated one superframe at a time, without ever forming the complete system (9). The attitude unknowns are thus successively eliminated simultaneously with the accumulation of (10). Practically, this requires that the observations are available superframe by superframe, i.e. chronologically, so that $(B'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa})^{-1}$ can be computed before observations in another superframe need to be processed. Further details about the accumulation and solution of (10) can be found in Ref. 2 and 4.

For the discrete attitude model ($n_{\kappa} = 0$), all matrices $B'_{\kappa\kappa}B_{\kappa\kappa}$ are of order 1×1 , and the system becomes slightly simpler. This is the basic solution method presently developed in Copenhagen.

Strict solution: elimination of abscissae

The above method is fairly efficient if there are many more attitude unknowns than abscissae and transformation coefficients, $N_{\Omega} \gg N_{\alpha} + N_d$. This is certainly the case for the discrete model ($N_{\Omega} \sim 20,000$, $N_{\alpha} \sim 2000$, $N_d \sim 20$ for a 12 hour set). With a high degree of dynamical smoothing, the number of attitude unknowns may be smaller by a factor 20 - 50. In this case it may be more efficient to eliminate the abscissae instead, leaving us with a contracted system of order $(N_{\Omega} + N_d)^2$. The procedure

is exactly analogous to the previous method, only with the the attitude unknowns and the abscissae exchanged. This requires that the observations are ordered according to star number (i), so that all observations pertaining to a given star can be summarized in the matrix equation

$$\mathbf{B}_i \Delta \alpha_i + \mathbf{C}_i \Delta \Omega + \mathbf{D}_i \Delta \mathbf{d} + \mathbf{v}_i = \mathbf{e}_i \quad (11)$$

with dimensions

$$\begin{array}{lll} \mathbf{B}_i(N_i, 1) & \Delta \alpha_i(1, 1) & \mathbf{v}_i(N_i, 1) \\ \mathbf{C}_i(N_i, N_\Omega) & \Delta \Omega(N_\Omega, 1) & \mathbf{e}_i(N_i, 1) \\ \mathbf{D}_i(N_i, N_d) & \Delta \mathbf{d}(N_d, 1) & \end{array}$$

Here N_i is the number of observations (in the set) of star i . Forming the contracted normals results is a system identical to (10), but with κ replaced by i and $\Delta \mathbf{a}$ by $\Delta \Omega$. Note that the $\mathbf{B}_i^t \mathbf{B}_i$ are scalars in this case.

Posterior smoothing

By this I mean a solution technique where the attitude smoothing is applied *after* the discrete solution. It could consist of the the following steps:

- (i) Make a discrete solution (without smoothing) for the unknowns $\{\alpha_i\}$, $\{\delta \Omega_k\}$, $\mathbf{d}$.
- (ii) Fit the smooth attitude representation, e.g. (5), to the discrete values $\delta \Omega_k$, resulting in a 'smoothed' attitude estimate $\delta \Omega(T)$.
- (iii) Make a new solution for $\{\alpha_i\}$ and $\mathbf{d}$ by assuming the above $\delta \Omega(T)$.

It can be shown (Ref. 5) that *if* step (ii) is carried out as a weighted least-squares solution, rigorously taking into account the full covariance of the discrete attitude estimate resulting from (i), *then* this procedure is mathematically equivalent to a strict solution.

In the following, let the caret ($\wedge$) signify the vectors and matrices involved in step (i), to the extent that they are different from those of the strict solution. Consider thus the discrete attitude estimate $\Delta \Omega^\wedge$ (a vector of length $N_f = \sum_{\kappa} m_{\kappa}$ = total number of frames in

the set) and its covariance matrix $\hat{V}$ (dimension $N_f \times N_f$). If the smoothing model (5) is written in matrix form

$$S \Delta\Omega + \mathbf{v} = \hat{\Delta}\Omega \quad (12)$$

where $\Delta\Omega$ is the N_Ω -vector of polynomial coefficients and $\mathbf{v}$ the residuals after the fit in step (ii), then the required solution is

$$\Delta\Omega = (S' \hat{V}^{-1} S)^{-1} S' \hat{V}^{-1} \hat{\Delta}\Omega \quad (13)$$

Therefore it is really the inverse of the covariance matrix which we need. An approximate expression for this inverse can be obtained quite easily if we neglect the unknowns $\mathbf{d}$ in (8). Writing the observation equation in scalar form, we have for the observation of star i in frame k ,

$$b_{ik} \hat{\Delta}\Omega_k + c_{ik} \Delta\alpha_i + v_{ik} = e_{ik} \quad (14)$$

The resulting normal equations matrix is of the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{\beta} & \mathbf{\gamma} \\ \mathbf{\gamma}' & \mathbf{\alpha} \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{\beta}$ and $\mathbf{\alpha}$ are diagonal matrices of dimension $N_f \times N_f$ and $N_\alpha \times N_\alpha$, respectively. Clearly $\hat{V}^{-1} = \mathbf{\beta} - \mathbf{\gamma}\mathbf{\alpha}^{-1}\mathbf{\gamma}'$, or explicitly

$$\left(\hat{V}^{-1} \right)_{k_1 k_2} = \delta_{k_1 k_2} \sum_{i \in k_1} b_{ik_1}^2 - \sum_{i \in k_1 \cap k_2} \left[b_{ik_1} b_{ik_2} c_{ik_1} c_{ik_2} / \sum_{k \in i} c_{ik}^2 \right] \quad (16)$$

$\delta_{k_1 k_2} = 1$ if and only if $k_1 = k_2$. $i \in k_1 \cap k_2$ means a star observed in both frames. It is seen that element (k_1, k_2) is different from zero only if at least one star has been observed in both frames. (This is not generally the case if the transformation unknowns $\mathbf{d}$ are introduced.)

The relative sparseness of $\hat{V}^{-1}$ suggests that it could be acceptable to neglect the correlations between different superframes, most of which have no stars in common anyway. In that case the least-squares fit of step (ii) could be made independently for each superframe, i.e.

$$\Delta\Omega_{\kappa} = \left[S'_{\kappa} (\hat{V}^{-1})_{\kappa\kappa} S_{\kappa} \right]^{-1} S'_{\kappa} (\hat{V}^{-1})_{\kappa\kappa} \hat{\Delta}\Omega_{\kappa} \quad (17)$$

if S and V^{-1} are suitably partitioned according to the superframe structure of step (ii).

3. PROPOSED TASK

The first part of the task is to produce the FORTRAN code for

- (A) the strict set solution with elimination of attitude, eqn (10), in a form which can be used both for the discrete case (one frame per superframe) and with an arbitrary superframe structure;
- (B) the posterior attitude smoothing of step (ii), including calculation of the weight matrices $(\hat{V}^{-1})_{\kappa\kappa}$ by means of (16);
- (C) the simplified set solution of step (iii), in which the attitude is fixed;
- (D) statistical comparison of abscissae between different solutions and between any solution and the true abscissae.

It may be convenient to combine at least (A) and (B) in a single program. Simulated input data (grid coordinates, approximate attitude, etc) will be available along with the 'true' abscissae and attitude. Subroutines for the function (3) and partial derivatives in (4) will also be given. It is sufficient to restrict the study to sets of 2 spin periods (about 1000 abscissae), in which case the normal equations can probably be handled directly in virtual memory and without reordering.

The second part of the task is to exploit these programs and study the accuracy and computational efficiency of the two smoothing methods (strict and posterior) as function of the degree of smoothing (i.e., the total number of attitude unknowns). For a given set of input data, solutions are made first for the discrete case, and then with both smoothing methods for increasing superframe length. The resulting abscissae are compared in different ways. The statistical analysis of abscissae errors should include correlation analysis as function of the angle between stars. The ultimate aims of this study are to investigate whether posterior smoothing is feasible and accurate enough, and to deduce the expected benefits and computational consequences of dynamical smoothing.

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